

Compaction to a Blue Nugget, SN feedback and BH Growth

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Compact Red Nuggets (RNs)

Damjanov+09

$z \sim 2$ $M \sim 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ $R_e \sim 1$ kpc low-SFR
the progenitors of the cores of today's Es?

Van Dokkum+08,10,14, Damjanov+09,11, Newman+10, Whitaker+12, Bruce+12, ...

Origin of Red Nuggets

High density due to early cosmological density?

Lilly & Carollo 16

$R_e \sim \lambda R_{\text{vir}}$ spin $\lambda \sim 0.04$ if angular momentum is conserved

Wet compaction: further dissipative contraction due to AM loss?

Dekel & Burkert 15, Zolotov+15

- Observed nuggets $R_e \sim 1 \text{ kpc} \sim 0.01 R_{\text{vir}}$ (64 x density)
- Wet compaction \rightarrow "blue" nuggets - compact, star forming progenitors

BNs exist! Peak at $z \sim 3$

Consistent in redshift, abundance, structure & kinematics with being the progenitors of the RNs

Barro+13-17, Williams+15, van Dokkum+15

"Blue" Nuggets

Barro+13-17
van Dokkum+ 15

Compact, star
forming, at $z \sim 2$

The BNs are
actually red...

Observed L-Shape Track

Barro+17

Wet Compaction

Dekel & Burkert 14, Zolotov+ 15

Inflow is "wet" if $\text{inflow} > \text{SFR}$

Wetness
parameter

$$w \equiv \frac{\text{inflow}}{\text{SFR}} \approx \varepsilon_{\text{sfr}}^{-1} f_{\text{cold}}^2 > 1$$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{sfr}} \leq 0.02 \quad f_{\text{cold}} \geq 0.2$$

Expect compact nuggets:

- at **high z**, where f_{gas} is high
- for **low spin** λ , where gas is denser
- when there is a trigger for **AM loss**

Cosmological Simulations

VELA by **Ceverino+** 10-17

Code: AMR ART (Kravtsov, Klypin)

Max resolution **25 pc**

5x35 galaxies zoom-in

SN and radiative feedback

+RAMSES, ENZO, GASOLINE

Collaborators:

Ceverino, Danovich, DeGraf, Freundlich, Inoue, Jiang, Lapiner,
Kretschmer, Mandelker, Roca-Fabrega, Tacchella, Tomassetti, Tweed,
Zolotov,

Bournaud+, Burkert+, Krumholz+, Primack+, Teyssier+,
Carollo+, Faber+, Genzel+

gas + young stars

stars

Compaction and quenching in the inner 1 kpc

Compaction and Quenching in Simulations

Zolotov+15
Tacchella+16
Dekel+17

Blue Nugget --> Red Nugget

dense gas core -> dense stellar core

gas depletion from core,
gas ring may form,
-> inside-out quenching

stellar core remains dense
from BN to RN

What is the Trigger of wet Compaction?

50% mergers, 30% no mergers

- Mergers (major, minor) (Barnes, Hernquist 91; Hopkins+ 06)
- VDI-driven inflow (Dekel, Burkert 15)
- Counter-rotating streams (Danovich+ 15)
- Tidal compression (Dekel+ 03; Renaud+ 14; Mandelker+ 16)
- Triaxial halo core (Ceverino+ 15; Tomassetti+ 16)
- Return of recycled low-AM gas (Elmegreen+ 14; DeGraf+ 16)

A Critical Mass for BN (at all z)

$$M_{\text{star}} \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$$

$$M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$$

Transition in Properties at the BN Phase

AD+17

	Pre-BN	BN	Post-BN
M_{star}	$<10^{9.5}$	$\sim 10^{10}$	$>10^{10}$
$R_e(M)$	slow rise	shrunk	rapid rise
SFR(M)	MS	top of MS	quenching through GV
t_{dep}		short	long
f_{gas}		high	low
$Z(M)$	rising	shoulder	constant
$V/\sigma_{\text{gas,star}}$	~ 1		~ 5 ~ 1
spin	low		high
center	DM-dominated		baryon-dominated
shape	elongated-prolate	compact disk	oblate
SN fdbk	effective		ineffective
BH-AGN	dormant	activated	growing - active
$\Sigma(r)$	diffuse	compact gas & stars	compact stars + gas ring
sSFR(r)	flat	declining	rising
$Z(r)$	gradual decline		steep decline
$A_v(r)$		central peak	extended

Evolution in $R_{\text{eff}}-M_*$ Stacked

Blue Nuggets: Compact Disks of Young Stars

V12 at $z=3.55$

Post-BN in Simulations: An Extended Clumpy Gas Ring around a Passive Core

The Compaction induces a Transition from DM to Baryonic Core

Dark-Matter Fraction inside R_e

Transition from DM to baryon dominance at BN

A Prolate Low-Mass Galaxy at $z=2.2$ in Sims

Gas: disk

Stars and DM: prolate

Consistent with
van der Wel+ 14
CANDELS

Transition of Shape: Prolate to Oblate

Ceverino+ 15 Tomassetti+ 16

The Universal Main Sequence of SFGs

MS ridge

$$sSFR_{MS} \approx 1.5 \text{ Gyr}^{-1} M_{*10}^{0.14} (1+z)_{z=3}^{5/2}$$

Deviation from MS ridge

$$\Delta_{MS} = \log(sSFR / sSFR_{MS})$$

Evolution About the Main Sequence in Sims

Evolution in the Main Sequence: Confinement and Bending at $10^{10} M_{\odot}$

Gradients across the Main Sequence

Gas Gradients across the Main Sequence

No gradients in stars

The Quenching Mechanism

Wet compaction:

$$\text{inflow} > \text{SFR} + \text{outflow}$$

Post-BN: high SFR and no gas supply to center

Central gas depletion

$$\text{inflow} < \text{SFR} + \text{outflow}$$

- disk shrunk \rightarrow no gas supply to center
- bulge suppresses VDI-driven inflow (morph. quench.)
- $V < 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ shallow potential \rightarrow outflows

The Quenching Mechanism

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Post-BN: high SFR and no gas supply to center
Central gas depletion

$$\text{inflow} < \text{SFR} + \text{outflow}$$

Long-term quenching?

- $\tau_{\text{deplete}} < \tau_{\text{replenish}} \quad z < 3$
- hot massive halo $M > 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$
- +AGN feedback

A Sequence of Compactions and Quenching Attempts

Shutdown of cold gas supply through hot massive halos

critical halo mass $\sim 10^{11.8} M_{\odot}$

$$t_{cool}^{-1} < t_{compress}^{-1}$$

M_{crit} by Shock Heating: $M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$

Dekel &
Birnboim 06

Simulations:
Ocvirk, Pichon,
Teyssier 08;
Dekel+ 09

Full Quenching vs Quenching Attempt

Empirical Model From Observations

Behroozi+ 17

The Quenching Mechanism

Wet compaction:

$$\text{inflow} > \text{SFR} + \text{outflow}$$

Post-BN: high SFR and no gas supply to center
Central gas depletion

$$\text{inflow} < \text{SFR} + \text{outflow}$$

If halo is less massive \rightarrow gas supply to a new disk
 \rightarrow new compaction and SFR ... until the halo is massive (hot)

If halo is massive (hot) \rightarrow starvation of gas supply
 \rightarrow long-term quenching +AGN feedback

A Characteristic Mass for Galaxy Formation

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$$M_{\text{star}} \sim 10^{10.5} M_{\odot} \quad M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{12} M_{\odot} \quad V_{\text{vir}} \sim 100 \text{ km/s}$$

- Hot CGM (virial shock heating) at $M > M_{\text{crit}}$

Rees & Ostriker 77, Silk 77, Binney 77, Dekel & Birnboim 06

- SN feedback efficient at $M < M_{\text{crit}}$ (V_{crit})

Larson 74, Dekel & Silk 86

- Blue Nuggets at M_{crit} (at all z)

Zolotov+15, Dekel+17

M_{crit} by SN Feedback: $M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$

Dekel &
Birnboim 06

Dekel & Silk 86

Interplay between SNe and BHs

RAMSES Simulation SN+BH by Dubois+ 15

- $M < M_{crit}$: strong SN fdbk suppresses BH growth
- Compaction overcomes SNe -> rapid BH growth
- $M > M_{crit}$: AGN fdbk helps quenching

Compaction driving BH Growth

New Horizon simulations SN+BH Dubois+ Lapiner+

EAGLE Simulations: Similar Results

Bower+ 2016

BH Growth by Compaction at $M_{\text{vir}} > 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$

- $M_{\text{vir}} < M_{\text{crit}}$, pre-compaction:
 - $V_{\text{esc}} < 100 \text{ km/s}$ -> SN winds of 100 km/s escape and evacuate the core
 - > BH growth is suppressed, BN formation is suppressed
- $M_{\text{vir}} \sim M_{\text{crit}}$, **compaction** (overcoming SN fdbk):
 - The compressed gas activates rapid BH growth
- $M_{\text{vir}} > M_{\text{crit}}$, post-compaction:
 - $V_{\text{esc}} > 100 \text{ km/s}$ -> SN winds are bound (by halo potential and hot gas)
 - > gas falls back in -> BH growth continues
 - > AGN self-regulates with the accretion,
AGN fdbk keeps the CGM hot and suppresses SFR

Observed High Fraction of AGN in BN Pase

Kocevski+17

-> Compaction triggers BH growth and AGN -> quenching

Conclusions

Galaxy scale $M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$ due to SN fbk and hot CGM

Wet compaction to a Blue Nugget - a dramatic event in many galaxies

Dissipative angular-momentum loss

by mergers, counter-rotating streams, violent disk instability, ...

BN \rightarrow quenching attempt, rejuvenation, confinement to the MS

Full quenching by hot CGM + AGN when $M_{\text{halo}} > M_{\text{crit}} \sim 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$

BN at $M_{*} \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ ($M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$, $V \sim 100$ km/s) when SN is ineffective

Post-BN: SFR in extended clumpy gas ring, or stellar envelope (ETG)

The BN marks transitions in most galaxy properties:

mass, size, kinematics, SFR, shape, gas frac., DM frac., metallicity, dust...

BNs are at the top of the MS, declining to Red Nuggets below the MS

\rightarrow gradients in galaxy properties across the MS for $M_{*} > 10^{10} M_{\odot}$

SN fdbk suppresses BH growth in $M < M_{\text{crit}}$ halos

Compaction triggers BH growth in $M > M_{\text{crit}}$ halos, SNe ineffective

Conclusions

Wet compaction to a Blue Nugget - a dramatic event in many galaxies

Compaction due to dissipative angular-momentum loss by mergers, counter-rotating streams, violent disk instability, ...

BN → quenching attempt, confined to the MS,
Full quenching by hot CGM + AGN fdbk when $M_{\text{halo}} > M_{\text{crit}} \sim 10^{11.5-12} M_{\odot}$

Major BN at $M_{*} \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ ($M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$, $V \sim 100$ km/s),
when SN fdbk becomes ineffective

Post-BN: SFR in extended clumpy gas ring, or stellar envelope (ETG)

The BN marks transitions in most galaxy properties:
mass, size, kinematics, SFR, shape, gas frac., DM frac., metallicity, dust...

BNs are at the top of the MS, declining through Green Ngts to Red Ngts
→ gradients in galaxy properties across the MS for $M_{*} > 10^{10} M_{\odot}$

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Wet compaction triggers BH growth in $M > M_{\text{crit}}$ halos, SNe ineffective

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Abundance of BNs

Model BN:

$M_{vir} > 10^{12} M_\odot$
 $\Delta t = 300 \text{ Myr}$
Major merger

Possible mismatch
in assumed
thresholds M_* , Σ_1

A Critical Mass for BN (at all z)

$$M_{\text{star}} \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$$

$$M_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^{11.5} M_{\odot}$$

Observed H α Rings

Genzel+ 14

Galaxy Spin

Transition of disk at the BN: from $V/\sigma \sim 1$ to $V/\sigma \sim 4$

gas

stars

Observed Central Baryon Dominance at $z \sim 2$ in $V > 100$ km/s Galaxies - Post Compaction?

Genzel+17

Obs. Galaxies at $z \sim 2$, $M < 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ are prolate

Van der Wel+ 14 CANDELS

The Main Sequence of SFGs: Confinement & Gradients Across

AGN Hosts are Compact

Chang+17

